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SAPEA Industry Innovation
Workshop Report

Advanced Materials

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SAPEA Industry Innovation Workshop Report

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Introduction

At the request of the European Commissioner for Startups, Research and Innovation, Ekaterina Zaharieva, the Group of Chief Scientific Advisors to the European Commission was tasked with preparing a Scientific Opinion on advanced materials. This work was supported by an Evidence Review Report delivered by SAPEA (Science Advice for Policy by European Academies), which provides the scientific foundation for the Advisors' recommendations.

Advanced materials are recognised as a key driver of the EU's industrial competitiveness and play a key role in supporting the twin green and digital transition. Despite their strategic importance, the European research and innovation ecosystem in this field remains fragmented, and the path from fundamental research to industrial application faces significant barriers. The European Commission has identified the need for stronger alignment between basic research and industrial needs, improved mechanisms for knowledge transfer, and enhanced cross-sector collaboration.

To ensure that the Evidence Review Report adequately reflects the perspectives and needs of industry, SAPEA organised an industry innovation workshop focused on advanced materials. The workshop took place on 4 June 2025 and engaged 17 stakeholders representing the advanced materials industry landscape and innovation chain. Participants explored practical solutions to strengthen the uptake of research into innovation and addressed systemic challenges in the field.

The workshop aimed to:

- Understand how innovative products can be developed from advanced materials research, addressing the gap between academic laboratories and industrial manufacturing.
- Evaluate the risks associated with investment in advanced materials research.
- Identify mechanisms to unlock new functionalities across sectors and stimulate new business models and innovation markets.
- Explore ways to enhance alignment and feedback loops between basic research and industrial needs, supporting the broader adoption of advanced materials by industry.

Details on the methodology and a list of participants are provided in the annex.

Disclaimer

This report captures the discussions, ideas, and viewpoints shared by 17 stakeholders from across the advanced materials industry and value chain. The views expressed reflect the participants' expertise and experience but have not undergone scientific validation. While this report contributes to the evidence review process of the SAPEA Advanced Materials working group, it represents initial stakeholder input rather than definitive findings. The report is presented in a collective, non-attributed manner and does not reflect the personal opinions of individual participants.

Findings from the workshop

Advanced materials are either new materials or derived from the modification of existing materials carrying new or improved structural and/or functional properties. There is a growing demand to design advanced materials that are energy-efficient, environmentally friendly, and cost-effective for building commonly used products and solving complex challenges like climate change and raw material deficits.

This workshop report summarises the perspectives of experts with experience in industry to identify systemic issues and potential solutions to accelerate innovation in the field of advanced materials.

The workshop aimed to identify important stakeholders and explore key challenges and barriers in bringing advanced materials from research to market in the European Union (EU).

1. Key stakeholders

The experts identified different stakeholders who are involved in the advanced materials sector. The stakeholders listed below either face challenges in the innovation process or have the power to alleviate challenges and create new solutions to accelerate the discovery, commercialisation, and adoption of advanced materials:

- **EU organisations and regulators:** the [European Commission](#) (EC); European academies; national standardisation bodies; [International Organization for Standardization](#) (ISO); the [European Committee for Standardization](#) (CEN); and Directorate-Generals (DGs) of the European Commission, in particular, [Environment \(ENV\)](#); [Internal Market, Industry, Entrepreneurship and SMEs \(GROW\)](#); and [Research and Innovation \(RTD\)](#).
- **Research organisations:** [Joint Research Centre](#) (JRC), academies, national research laboratories, universities, [Materials Research Society](#), [Psi-k Network](#).
- **Funding agencies:** [European Research Council](#) (ERC), [Horizon Europe](#), [Austrian Research Promotion Agency](#) (FFG), [German Research Foundation](#) (DFG), other national and multinational public funding organisations.
- **Industry and small and medium enterprises (SMEs):** Manufacturers, industry associations, raw materials manufacturers, startups and spin-offs.
- **Innovation ecosystem:** Incubators, supercomputing centres, artificial intelligence (AI) factories, networking and matchmaking platforms.
- **Investors:** Private investors, venture capital, financial institutions.
- **Civil society and product end users.**
- **Others:** People affected by environmental pollution, indigenous and underrepresented populations, and communities involved in raw materials production.

2. Challenges

Researchers and manufacturers aim to develop advanced materials with unique functionality and improved efficiency. However, they face numerous challenges that hinder progress in the development, deployment, manufacturing, and integration of advanced materials. Experts identified the following challenges.

2.1. Innovation

Innovation is a multi-stage process that transforms new ideas and goals into functional products for the market. Access to funding throughout all the stages of innovation remains a key challenge in advanced materials discovery.

Materials discovery sometimes occurs by chance through a long development process, and it is difficult to maintain stable long-term funding until the product becomes marketable. While the EU has established important regulatory frameworks, the current processes within structured and multi-layered institutions can sometimes limit rapid access to funding for early-stage innovation. In addition, materials science research often receives less public and institutional attention compared to research areas such as AI and quantum computing, making the field less attractive to new funding that could generate a robust innovation ecosystem.

A lack of steady funding also contributes to a dearth of talent in the field. This, in turn, results in a smaller but more expensive pool of highly skilled individuals, which makes it harder for organisations to recruit and retain the expertise needed to move projects efficiently through innovation pipelines. In addition, advanced materials research is an interdisciplinary field, and the lack of people with interdisciplinary skills can seriously hamper innovation processes, such as market adoption, developing guidelines for regulatory compliance, and envisioning material integration in end products.

The lack of raw materials and suitable alternatives remains a serious hurdle for innovation. For example, there is no obvious replacement for per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS), a group of substances that represents a critical material in numerous applications. While there is a demand for and interest in shifting from fossil-based raw materials to sustainable bio-based or recycled alternatives, they introduce significant cost and performance challenges. These bio-based and recycled materials alternatives are currently expensive and may require more complex processing, offsetting potential energy savings.

The integration of advanced materials into end products often takes place within closed, proprietary frameworks. Unfortunately, there are not enough open data and pipelines available for new applications, making it difficult to employ advanced characterisation techniques under dynamic conditions for testing and benchmarking.

While European entities actively patent relevant inventions in the advanced materials field, the process of patenting has its own challenges. In particular, a discrepancy often exists between the perceived strength of a patent and the actual investable opportunity it represents. This mismatch can stifle

investment in potentially impactful discoveries and contribute to the 'valley of death', where many innovations fail to reach the commercialisation stage.

Lastly, outdated regulatory practices and standards in critical research areas impact the adoption of novel solutions. Policy frameworks for such ever-evolving fields are often perceived as fragmented and unclear, further delaying the approval of advanced materials on the market.

2.2. Scalability

Once an advanced material is synthesised and its applications are understood, it is imperative to assess the feasibility and pathways for scaling it for market deployment.

Synthesising materials at scale for industrial applications at a reasonable cost is a key challenge. Scaling up is a multi-step process, and numerous technical challenges arise at each step related to the speed of the scale-up process, energy demand, quality control, and regulatory hurdles. Collectively, these factors create a fundamental scaling limit for each material that is further exacerbated by the lack of necessary infrastructure, resources, and bottlenecks throughout the scale-up process.

In certain instances, scaling up is feasible; however, it might not be economically viable for the company, at least in the early stages of development. In addition, different industries require different amounts of material, but the lack of appropriate business models in relevant industries' use cases may impede scaling up.

2.3. Academic systems

While academic research laboratories drive innovation in advanced materials, the way academia operates can pose challenges for innovation.

First, the current academic funding model does not offer enough money to innovate new materials attractive to the industry. Academia also often does not support high-risk projects due to funding and resource limitations, resulting in fewer avenues for advanced materials research and product development.

Academic researchers often pursue research to gain knowledge rather than designing projects with immediate commercial objectives or specific applications. Academics also do not apply strict goal-setting or assess key performance indicators (KPIs) of project advancement as industry researchers do. In addition, academia offers very few programmes that train transdisciplinary scientists, creating an overall lack of the skilled workforce essential in the highly diverse advanced materials field.

2.4. Industry systems

Industry operates to build products at scale for consumers, but several factors and limitations get in the way of commercialising advanced materials.

Findings from the workshop

Industry is still risk-averse when it comes to advanced materials. The number of investors who commit to complex and untested ideas remains very low. Venture capitalists do not always invest in startups they perceive as risky, especially when it may take a long time to see a return on investment. Within the EU, there are fewer investment opportunities in advanced materials than in other regions, limiting the growth and attractiveness of the advanced materials industry.

Europe does not have many end-use companies (product buyers), and some governments show little interest in buying new advanced materials. In contrast, the US and Chinese governments are the first purchasers of materials, creating a stronger market and greater confidence in advanced materials products in those countries. It is challenging to set up purchasing contracts at the same scale with governments in Europe because individual EU states do not have defence budgets comparable to those of the US and China.

Industry also tends to be insular, where people work on specific tasks without diversifying tasks or funding. Moreover, companies frequently rely on a closed innovation model, attempting to solve all challenges internally rather than partnering with other organisations working on similar problems.

While new machine learning (ML) and AI technologies are gaining popularity across all sectors, industry lacks experts in advanced simulation and modelling tools vital to automation.

2.5. Synergy between academia and industry

Academia and industry rely on each other to transform new ideas into successful products. However, the lack of strong collaborative practices to unite the two main driving forces of innovation contributes to a lack of commercialisation.

Academia and industry remain rather disjointed ecosystems, lacking cooperative and integrated research environments and trusted networks to drive industrial solutions. For example, few incubators facilitate startups in academia. Academic startups do not involve industry in the early stages of the discovery process. Startups typically build products in isolation and communicate with industry too late to address scalability and market adoption problems. Moreover, academia and industry in Europe communicate indirectly, via conferences and publications. In contrast, Chinese industry closely partners with academia and startups from the early stages of advanced materials research, thereby building better and long-term, viable innovation synergies and products.

There is also a lack of an entrepreneurship ecosystem in the EU, which makes it difficult to build materials startups beyond research labs. As of today, only a handful of institutions, like the [EPFL](#), offer robust support to materials startups.

2.6. Data pitfalls

Research is data-driven, and inadequate and imperfect data pipelines can impact the efficiency, speed, and accuracy of the innovation and manufacturing processes. The lack of comprehensive, high-

quality datasets is a challenge in several areas of advanced materials research. In addition, academics disseminate research information through journal articles, often presented in unstructured formats, making it difficult to extract data in a reliable and reproducible manner.

Moreover, ongoing efforts to utilise data for advanced materials discovery are insufficient in leveraging predictive modelling tools. Fewer experts in the advanced materials field can trace and explain hallucinations arising from AI predictions and troubleshoot them to support materials discovery.

2.7. Geopolitics

The production and processing of materials require raw materials, resources, and technologies that are often unavailable due to geopolitical constraints. There is uncertainty in the supply of critical raw materials due to the ever-changing geopolitical landscape. While there are supply chain arrangements between EU countries, countries with isolationist or nationalistic policies can affect the flow of critical materials and impact discovery.

Europe also largely ignores competition from China and the US and lacks a strategy aimed at global leadership. European Commission projects are less competitive and ambitious compared to their Chinese and American counterparts, such as those supported by the [US Department of Energy](#) and [Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency \(DARPA\)](#).

3. Barriers blocking the adoption of advanced materials from laboratory to market

The experts explored the main roadblocks preventing the successful uptake of advanced materials in Europe. The barriers outlined here relate to the people involved in the process, pipelines required to make advancements, technical challenges, as well as policy and funding decisions.

3.1. People

The advanced materials workforce is often trained in traditional disciplines because universities have rigid training programmes that do not always evolve with the needs of industry. There is also a knowledge gap in the existing workforce, especially in SMEs, where workers are not aware of new developments and have few opportunities to upskill. Many SMEs operate on a small scale and struggle to recruit, train, and retain skilled personnel. SMEs run by families also fail to transfer critical skills to the younger generation. Moreover, there is a dearth of engineers, scientists, and researchers trained to use new digital tools.

Findings from the workshop

Research communities lack entrepreneurship skills and experience. Basic research and applied sciences communities mostly work in isolation, without mediators with industry. Similarly, innovators lack the necessary education in complex areas of technology development, market needs, and investment dynamics. Innovators and investors also do not use the proper channels and language to effectively communicate and collaborate with research communities. This can sometimes lead to investors inaccurately assessing product utility, contributing to elevated expectations for products that are not yet ready for widespread market adoption. For instance, while nanomaterials have been researched extensively over many years, only a select few have achieved scalable commercial production.

There is too much reliance on reviewers and evaluators to make funding decisions in Europe. In addition, there is a stark knowledge gap in organisations making funding decisions. Reviewers often lack the skills and vision to recognise projects that are high risk but high impact, especially in the advanced materials field. For example, the [BIG-Map Project](#), a European battery interface development programme, faltered due to an inefficient evaluation process. Cutting-edge, disruptive technologies in the BIG-Map Project were evaluated by reviewers who did not have the expertise and knowledge to understand the new concepts and ideas presented to them. In addition, programme managers on such big projects often lack the expertise and experience to overcome regulatory and bureaucratic barriers.

3.2. Process

Materials discovery requires surveying broad research areas with many unknowns. When scalability and reliability are not emphasised early in the research and discovery processes, newly synthesised materials—no matter how advanced—fail to translate into real-world applications. For example, a research project may successfully synthesise milligrams of a material with potential applications in the industry; however, industry requires the material in kilograms. If the tools or processes used to synthesise the material are not amenable to scaling up, the material remains inaccessible to industry. Therefore, ignoring scalability and transferability to industry at the early stages of the discovery process hinders new material adoption in the market.

Additionally, infrastructure, machinery, and manufacturing processes are simply not available for specific advanced material development and scale-up. It is also challenging to replace existing supply chains and work pipelines to incorporate specific advanced materials. Moreover, current tools and processes for manufacturing and scaling up advanced materials are not well adapted for use in SMEs.

Timeline expectations for projects vary between academic research institutes and industry. Industry typically requires results much faster. In many cases, academics develop complex processes that do not function in the industry setting in a required timeframe.

European open science and innovation policies require transparency in many aspects of discovery and development, which can sometimes slow the pace of innovation. For example, the requirement to build and publish innovation roadmaps and documentation can delay commercialisation, a step that is not mandated in countries like China. In such instances, closed innovation ecosystems may enable faster market deployment.

Data ecosystems are fragmented and non-standardised for advanced materials, making it difficult to integrate modelling processes in experimental validation. There is also low digital maturity in advanced materials research and development (R&D) pipelines. In addition, a lack of high-quality data on how materials change and how these changes affect scale-up and production protocols makes it difficult to effectively use computational methods to solve challenges in industrial implementation.

There is a gap between industry needs and the current European Commission [safe-and-sustainable-by-design](#) (SSbD) guidelines. Such guidelines and other compliance frameworks within the EU are complex and resource-intensive for early-stage product development, particularly for SMEs.

3.3. Technology

The technology required for scaling up advanced materials is often unavailable. Similarly, available scale-up technologies might be affected by practical barriers, such as the speed of production, process quality, and regulations, limiting their suitability for large-scale applications. There is also no available technology for recycling major composite and hybrid materials.

Prospective life cycle assessment (LCA) is a process that estimates the future environmental impact of technologies and their products. Such assessments are necessary but challenging and uncertain due to the limited availability of technologies, especially at the early stages of technology development.

[Technology readiness levels](#) (TRLs) describe the different development stages of a technology, product, or service on a scale from 1 to 9. Building a product and understanding it at each stage of the TRL in real-world settings is critical. However, the technologies required to perform testing at each TRL stage might not exist. For example, the advanced materials industry invests and develops test methods for each TRL level to comply with regulations. Often, a material needs to be dispersed as part of a test. However, dispersal methods are not available for hydrophobic materials. In such instances, the lack of technology results in the company's inability to conduct the test, which directly affects its ability to meet regulatory demands and successfully launch a product.

3.4. Policy

There remains limited governmental support for coordinated regulatory frameworks when compared to China, making it difficult to align and collaborate effectively with countries both within and outside the EU. Due to fragmented policies, important stakeholders across research, industry, and regulation cannot be integrated into a single network.

Moreover, the EU regulatory framework poses administrative complexity affecting investment. European regulatory obligations are numerous and stringent. Companies often struggle to comply with or navigate them successfully, particularly due to limitations in available technologies, materials, and skilled personnel.

Findings from the workshop

There is increased pressure on industry to adopt sustainable practices; however, there are no clear guidelines on how to achieve this for advanced materials. For SMEs, regulatory requirements might be even more difficult to accomplish. In some cases of new chemical development, the environmental regulations are often seen as too stringent.

Failure is inevitable in research and discovery. However, many states do not actively support this aspect of innovation. For example, the Chinese government invests in mechanisms that help companies share risks and enable them to fail faster and effectively. Military and government agencies support large science parks that have collective expertise and scale-up capabilities. In such systems, there is a constant evaluation of failure, with companies terminated when they do not meet their objectives and funding then becoming available to new companies. There are no such fail-safe mechanisms with state support in Europe, leading to the wastage of resources from Horizon Europe and other public funding schemes on companies that are unlikely to be commercially viable.

Complex, opaque, and lengthy patents and IP rights processes are money and time sinks. While timelines vary, filing a patent, in some cases, may take an average of two to three years in Europe. In contrast, competitors in China, India, Korea, and other countries are surpassing the EU's technology levels by focusing on technological advancement rather than prioritising patent filing. While patents are essential for protecting innovations, they can also create monopolies that may disadvantage certain stakeholders, particularly SMEs. Moreover, evolving EU policies may complicate the adoption of advanced materials by creating IP-related conflicts between institutions.

There might be a lack of public acceptance (or social licensing) when it comes to mining, processing, and factories in advanced materials. This means that even legally approved projects could face delays or opposition from communities or the public, which can hinder the development and deployment of advanced materials.

3.5. Funding and investment

There is an overall lack of long-term public funding and industry investments for infrastructure and new technology development. There is also a lack of funding for infrastructure maintenance and developing a viable market for new materials. Such long-term investments are vital for innovation because the development phase for materials is long, taking roughly 10–15 years before a company begins to profit. The US and China invest rapidly and take high risks, providing substantial funding within a short timeframe to establish production lines. Such schemes and policies are not available in the EU. There is also a lack of big defence investments like [DARPA](#), a funding mechanism by the US Department of Defense to support materials discovery.

Funding streams do not support a smooth transition from R&D to commercialisation. For example, scaling up from academic pilot projects to new companies requires large investments that remain scant in Europe. Typically, research institutes make discoveries with the support of public funding. Once a new product becomes available and works at a smaller scale, private companies invest heavily to scale the product for wide commercial adoption. However, public funding is often insufficient when the project is

no longer at the discovery stage, and, at the same time, large companies are not willing to invest heavily because they are unsure about the scalability and return on investment. This stage is called the 'valley of death'. Most ventures fail to cross the valley of death due to the lack of long-term funding specifically needed to move forward in scale-up and commercialisation. When companies do not successfully navigate this phase, it often results in a significant loss of knowledge and skills that can be difficult, if not impossible, to recover.

In research, funding schemes tend to be narrowly focused and have restricted budgets, which can limit support for more experimental or exploratory projects. Additionally, public funding processes often involve extended timelines for decision-making and grant disbursement.

4. Solutions

Participants suggested the following solutions related to policy, funding, and regulation to mitigate the challenges associated with progress in advanced materials in the EU.

4.1. Developing networks

The development of new platforms is required to facilitate communication between all stakeholders. First, create trusted network clusters that bridge academia and industry. These networks can provide a better understanding of the value chain processes and business models for streamlining the commercialisation process, starting at the discovery stage. Incentivising cooperation and co-creation should be a prerequisite for these trusted networks.

In addition, the European Commission and EU policymakers can directly oversee these trusted networks by creating working groups focused on specific objectives and topics, such as worker safety and consumer safety issues, to obtain long-term solutions for problems in material discovery. For example, research programmes that lack scientific knowledge in waste management can work with specific focus groups to gain greater competency in this area.

Foster cooperation between industry and academia by sharing research results through expedited IP agreements and facilitating the transfer of promising material research outcomes across different sectors. Similarly, industry can adopt open innovation frameworks by jointly creating IPs for manufacturing and scaling up rather than competing to solve the same problems.

Establish networks that connect small companies with large corporations to enable large corporations to leverage external innovation instead of developing technology in-house, while allowing smaller companies to benefit from the infrastructure and scaling capabilities of larger partners. In addition, create mentoring platforms for industry, where experts from successful materials companies can share models and best practices with other companies interested in advanced materials.

Findings from the workshop

For example, [Open Innovation Test Beds](#) is a network of entities established between EU Member States, providing common access to physical facilities, capabilities, and services necessary for the development, testing, and upscaling of nanotechnology and advanced materials in industrial environments.

4.2. Building partnerships between academia, industry, and end users

Use science parks and academic incubators to build fruitful partnerships between academia and industry. University-based incubators can support the creation of startups and spin-offs, which then benefit from integration into science and technology parks. These environments provide access to mentoring, infrastructure, and scale-up opportunities. Incubators may also specialise in targeted applications, for example, acceleration platforms dedicated to advanced tribological techniques (friction, lubrication, and wear) or material characterisation methods.

4.3. Funding and investment

Invest substantially in public and private funding in advanced materials R&D as well as product scale-up technologies and infrastructure. Prioritise and offer project-based funding to promising, new ideas developed by young researchers and strengthen collaborative projects for senior researchers with a strong track record in the field. In addition, create open-ended, experimental funding schemes without rigid outcome requirements to allow flexibility during the research and innovation process. Moreover, develop fast-track, separate funding schemes for scaling up and passing through the valley of death. Importantly, facilitate open evaluations to accelerate funding access and allow international capital to flow towards innovative companies.

Develop new models of academic training and research capacity-building that combine academic and industry funding. Importantly, invest in emerging technologies and materials interfaces to develop materials with improved performance designed for circularity and new applications.

Clearly define specific research areas of importance and comprehensively finance the full research cycle in those areas. Define grand challenges with specific, achievable milestones within such funding schemes. For example, allocate a separate funding pool for projects and techniques that predict SSbD materials during discovery.

Establish a European equivalent of DARPA for advanced materials targeting defence and commercial applications. Replicate funding mechanisms from other big economies that help successfully drive innovation in advanced materials.

Participants recognised the following examples as successful funding schemes from Canada and the US, which showcase how to remove funding constraints for innovators in the advanced materials space.

Example 1: The IC6 mission innovation workshop report on materials acceleration platforms identified an open opportunity for combining experimental automation and AI to develop autonomous platforms. However, none of the member countries had a viable funding mechanism to support work on such a rapidly emerging technology. Canada, one of the member countries, allocated 6 million Canadian dollars in funding to support researchers at the University of British Columbia and the University of Toronto to develop [Project Ada](#), which has now successfully culminated into a 500 million dollar acceleration consortium, the [Canada First Research Excellence Fund](#), to develop user facilities creating autonomous platforms.

Example 2: The Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency (DARPA) is a research and development agency of the United States Department of Defense that funds research programmes in the development of materials. Their funding mechanism allows for rapid distribution of money, requiring only short grant proposals of two to four pages. Such a system decreases the time required to evaluate proposals and disburse funds by a few months. In addition, the programme managers of these grants can focus on driving innovation and supporting new ideas without worrying about failure. This mechanism may have supported an increase in new materials entering the US advanced materials industry.

Example 3: Self-Driving Labs (SDLs) reduce the time and cost of bringing advanced materials to market. The Acceleration Consortium, awarded 200 million Canadian dollars by the Canada First Research Excellence Fund, allocates yearly grants via a flexible procedure that supports researchers at various project stages and disburses grant money promptly.

4.4. Research culture

Reform current academic practices. First, adapt how research is conducted and documented to better capture failures, negative results, and knowledge gained from mistakes and troubleshooting. For example, support journals that publish failed research in advanced materials. In addition, foster the adoption of FAIR (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) data-sharing principles across the research community. Revise academic curricula to integrate transdisciplinary skills and approaches.

Promote research programmes that accelerate the green transition by embedding sustainability principles into scientific practice, where researchers prioritise materials and processes that support net-zero carbon emissions.

Social acceptance and citizen engagement are key factors in the successful adoption of advanced materials innovations. Trust, public perception, and effective communication can shape stakeholder support. Establish and regain the trust of EU citizens in emerging technologies, such as genetic engineering for biomaterials, fission and fusion technologies for energy needs, and green fuels, through citizen engagement and the transparent dissemination of information.

4.5. Fiscal and economic measures

Offer tax incentives to encourage companies to use sustainable advanced materials. For example, provide subsidies to companies making greener products and offer consumer tax reductions. These tax benefits could enhance market acceptance of such solutions, supporting advanced materials companies in generating revenue despite the higher costs often associated with developing and producing sustainable materials.

4.6. Policy and regulatory changes

Establish a dedicated advisory and strategic body within the EU to support policymakers in continuously developing and refining strategies to achieve European sovereignty in advanced materials, especially in critical areas like energy. In addition, create long-term collaborative frameworks that bring together multiple institutions supporting advanced materials within and outside of the EU.

Develop a single advanced materials innovation roadmap for Europe, outlining a strategic vision and standard business practices. Ensure that international regulatory frameworks support the roadmap, avoiding fragmentation that could limit global competitiveness.

Reduce bureaucracy for high-risk, high-impact research and innovation projects and technologies being developed within the EU. In addition, streamline bureaucratic procedures that are difficult to interpret or apply consistently. Focus on creating transparent value chain processes that accelerate progress in development and commercialisation.

Align the regulatory and innovation activities of relevant European Commission Directorates-General to ensure consistent support for advanced materials development. Implement strategies for safe and sustainable innovation, as outlined by the [Malta Initiative](#), while addressing trade barriers by developing internationally harmonised test methods. Similarly, establish monitoring bodies to track market and R&D trends and use these insights to ensure regulatory alignment.

Identify areas within advanced materials that are ripe for the green and digital transitions and promote recyclability with traceability in these domains. In addition, simplify standardisation, qualification, and certification processes across different industries and incentivise industries to obtain SSbD certifications.

4.7. Data innovation

Develop a leading European AI company, such as [Mistral](#), to implement new computation techniques and foundation models. Moreover, support the development of ML and other AI tools specific to optimisation processes in the advanced materials industry.

Build and deploy databases similar to [Materials Commons](#) to create digital profiles of materials for academic and industrial applications. Similarly, create an international community of data modellers and train materials scientists in data science applications.

5. Summary

The participants consolidated the insights gained from the discussion and ranked solutions based on their impact and feasibility; this offers stakeholders a clear prioritisation of actions to solve challenges plaguing advanced materials innovation in the EU.

High impact and high feasibility solutions	High impact but low feasibility solutions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Create fast-track funding schemes ● Facilitate the transfer of positive results between sectors ● Develop larger-scale EU-funded projects ● Reduce bureaucracy for high-risk, high-impact research applications in the EU ● Develop a single innovation and business roadmap for advanced materials ● Promote FAIR-compliant data sharing ● Facilitate infrastructure accessibility across the value chain during new materials development 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Define topical areas clearly and finance them comprehensively ● Identify domains in materials relevant to green and digital transitions ● Promote recyclability with traceability ● Create funding schemes without rigid outcome requirements ● Develop complex networks of innovators, investors, and market players ● Establish mechanisms to monitor advanced materials R&D and market trends across the EU ● Provide taxation benefits to support sustainable yet high-cost advanced materials ● Establish a European sovereign fund for innovation in advanced materials that resembles DARPA ● Support journals of failed research to document processes that did not work ● Create standardised digital profiles of all materials ● Simplify and align standardisation and certification processes across industry ● Facilitate collaboration between academia and industry in the context of IP agreements and the exchange of confidential information

Annex 1: Methods

Overview

A workshop on industry innovation in advanced materials was held to gather industry perspectives and inform the development of the SAPEA Evidence Review Report (ERR). The session brought together experts from across sectors to explore key challenges and opportunities related to the development and deployment of advanced materials. The workshop was conducted in line with the priorities identified in the scoping paper on advanced materials.

The objectives of the workshop were to explore how innovative products could be developed from advanced materials research, particularly addressing the gap between academic laboratories and industrial manufacturing; to assess the risks associated with investment in this field; to identify mechanisms for unlocking the potential of new functionalities across sectors and stimulating business model innovation; and to examine how alignment and feedback loops between basic research and industrial needs could be improved to support the uptake of advanced materials by industry.

As part of its contribution to the Evidence Review Report, the workshop aimed to define a clear set of best practices for developing innovative products from advanced materials research and to identify key barriers in bridging the gap between laboratories and manufacturing. It also sought to highlight specific challenges related to investment risks and explore strategies to address them. In addition, participants discussed mechanisms to unlock the potential of new functionalities across sectors and applications, along with ways to stimulate new business models and innovation markets. Finally, the workshop aimed to identify best practices for improving alignment and feedback loops between basic research and industrial needs, as well as strategies to support the uptake of advanced materials by industry.

Participant selection

The workshop brought together a diverse group of 17 stakeholders representing the advanced materials industry landscape and value chain. This included:

- Stakeholders who identify challenges and bottlenecks,
- Scientific experts familiar with these bottlenecks,
- Researchers studying startups failures and their underlying causes,
- Representatives from large companies as well as SMEs, startups, and spin-offs,
- Experts with experience in specific fields such as health, mobility, electronics, construction, and energy, including specialists in biomaterials, nanomaterials, graphene, polymers, electronics (notably chips and semiconductors), and batteries.

SAPEA staff compiled an internal list of 145 industry stakeholders from various advanced materials initiatives, stakeholder mappings, and desk research. The selection process and resulting list (125

names) were approved by the SAPEA Board in May 2025. Invitations were then extended to those on the A and B lists who met the selection criteria outlined above. To ensure comprehensive coverage, additional names were later added to the list to fill gaps, primarily through targeted desk research conducted by SAPEA staff.

Efforts were made to ensure balanced gender representation and wide geographical coverage, including participation from widening countries. The final invitee list comprised 41.2% male and 58.8% female participants. Due to a last-minute substitution caused by illness, the actual attendees included 11 men (64.7%) and 6 women (35.3%). Four of the 17 participants (23.5%) were from widening countries.

Additionally, some members of the working group attended the workshop as active observers. Their role was to take notes, ask questions, and summarise key points to ensure that the workshop outcomes effectively contributed to the development of the Evidence Review Report. Several members of the SAM Secretariat also attended as observers and were invited to ask questions. In addition, several members of the SAPEA staff supported the workshop organisation and acted as breakout session moderators.

Workshop format

The workshop was held online in a discussion-based format designed to encourage active participation. The structure and agenda were developed by a facilitator experienced in planning and moderating participatory online discussions for stakeholders in science and industry and were approved and refined in collaboration with SAPEA staff.

Moderated discussions were supported by a Miro board to enable collaborative input. Sessions were facilitated by the external workshop facilitator, external moderators, and SAPEA staff.

The format featured several interactive elements, including participant self-introductions, an icebreaker exercise to generate initial ideas, structured breakout sessions using tools such as a fishbone diagram and stakeholder mapping, a stakeholder perspectives activity, a collaborative solution sprint with idea clustering, prioritisation through an impact–feasibility matrix, and a final plenary for presenting bold ideas and individual reflections.

The workshop was conducted under the Chatham House Rule. Participants were informed that the names of experts attending would only be published with the release of the workshop report and were asked to agree not to contact working group members after the workshop regarding the preparation of the ERR and its contents.

Before the workshop, participants received an information sheet and agenda outlining the background and format, alongside a copy of the scoping paper, a draft SAPEA literature review on advanced materials, and a draft policy landscape on advanced materials.

Annex 1: Methods

As both experts and working group members participated, the latter received separate instructions on their role. Since the aim was to gather expert views, working group members were tasked with asking probing questions, taking notes, and identifying gaps, rather than leading the discussion.

Processing workshop outputs and reporting

The workshop was recorded for transcription and internal viewing. In addition, the main ideas were captured on the Miro board for each session. Following the industry innovation workshop, a meeting with the working group was held to debrief and incorporate key discussion points into upcoming working group meetings.

Annex 2: Agenda

Time	Activity	Description
12:30—12:40	Welcome	Introduction by Prof. Anke Weidenkaff & Prof. Olli Ikkala , co-chairs of the SAPEA working group on advanced materials, and Geoffroy Delamare , Policy Officer, EC, DG RTD, SAM.
12:40—12:50	What to expect & agenda walk-through	Introduction of the facilitation team, walk-through of the session flow, participant expectations, and instructions for using Miro. Led by Krishna Reddy , workshop facilitator.
12:50—13:10	Participant introductions	Each participant briefly shares their name; current role; country of residence; and any other relevant affiliations, roles, or interests in advanced materials.
13:10—13:30	Icebreaker	Participants share the first challenge or opportunity that comes to mind when thinking about innovation in advanced materials.
13:30—14:20	Breakout: Mapping barriers (fishbone)	Participants identify key systemic barriers to bringing advanced materials from lab to market. They use a fishbone diagram to explore challenges across areas such as policy, industry practices, research collaboration, investment and funding, workforce skills, and sustainability.
14:20—14:35	Identifying key stakeholders	Participants map the individuals, groups, or organisations involved in —or affected by— the barriers identified earlier. They build a shared view of who influences, enables, or is impacted by challenges along the path from research to market.
14:35—14:50	Break	N/A
14:50—15:15	Breakout: stakeholder perspectives	Participants take a closer look at the barriers identified earlier by examining how they are experienced by those who play a role in the innovation process. This session is not about solving the problems faced but about better understanding the system dynamics that shape progress from research to industry innovation.
15:15—15:45	Solution sprint & sorting	Participants brainstorm mechanisms to address the barriers identified earlier and support industry innovation in advanced materials. Ideas are then grouped into key action areas for further evaluation.
15:45—16:05	Prioritising solutions (Impact/ Feasibility matrix)	Participants assess proposed solutions to identify those with the greatest impact and most practical implementation potential.
16:05—16:25	Plenary share: bold ideas presentation	Groups present their bold solutions to promote industry innovation in advanced materials.
16:25—16:40	Final reflection & takeaways	Participants reflect on insights and identify key takeaways.

Annex 3: List of participants and other attendees

Experts

- Vitor Abrantes, GRAPHENEST, Portugal
- Antreas Afantitis, NovaMechanics, Cyprus
- Carolina Aguilar, INBRAIN Neuroelectronics, Spain/Switzerland
- Elmar Bonaccorso, Airbus, Germany
- Nicolas Cudre-Mauroux, SICPA, Switzerland
- Gillian Davis, MatCelerate ZERO / Cambridge Enterprises, United Kingdom
- Claudia Eggert, German Federal Institute for Materials Research and Testing, Germany
- André Gzásó, Austrian Nanoinformation Commission, Austria
- Jason Hattrick-Simpers, CanmetMATERIALS, Canada
- Danail Hristozov, GreenDecision / EMERGE Ltd., Italy/Bulgaria
- Amaya Igartua, TEKNIKER / EUMAT / Alliance for Materials (A4M), Spain
- Blaž Likozar, National Institute of Chemistry, Slovenia
- Marcin Lewenstein, InnoEnergy, Netherlands
- Alexander Madgwick, AM IP & Technology Services, United Kingdom
- Anna Pellizzari, MATERIALLY, Italy
- Sean Kelly, Nanotechnology Industries Association, Belgium
- Annika Ölme, SKF, Sweden

Group of Chief Scientific Advisors (Observers)

- Nicole Grobert, former member of the Group of Chief Scientific Advisors (2018–2025)

Working group members in attendance on advanced materials

- Anke Weidenkaff, Technical University of Darmstadt (co-chair)
- Olli Ikkala, Aalto University (co-chair)
- Angélique Léonard, University of Liège
- Sabrina Sartori, University of Oslo
- Nicola Marzari, École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne
- Astrid Heidemann Lassen, Aalborg University
- Wei Sha, Queens University Belfast
- Luca M. Ghiringhelli, University of Erlangen-Nuremberg
- Robert Dominko, University of Ljubljana

Annex 3: List of participants and other attendees

- David Cahen, Weizmann Institute of Science
- Steffen Foss Hansen, Technical University Denmark
- Norbert Babcsán, Innobay Hungary Ltd
- Luca Valentini, University of Padua
- Christoph Helbig, University of Bayreuth
- Laura Rodriguez-Lorenzo, International Iberian Nanotechnology Laboratory (INL)
- Merja Penttilä, VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland
- Andrew Barry, University College London

SAPEA Board and staff

- Rudolf Hielscher, SAPEA Manager
- Hannah Macdonald, Scientific Policy Officer for FEAM
- Mariana Rei, Scientific Policy Officer for Euro-CASE
- Frederico Rocha, Scientific Policy Officer for EASAC
- Carly Seedall, Scientific Policy Officer for Academia Europaea
- Louise Edwards, Scientific Policy Officer for Academia Europaea

Science Policy, Advice and Ethics Unit at DG RTD, European Commission

- Ingrid Zegers, Team Lead
- Geoffroy Delamare, Policy Officer

Science writer

- Sejal Davla

Workshop facilitation staff

- Samrat Bose, breakout room moderator
- Swaroop Rao, breakout room moderator
- Krishna Reddy, workshop facilitator

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